

**The English language is to speak speech activity type and talk that
develops the factors.**

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ANNOTATSIYA

This article 's talkspeech activity type and talk that develops the factors about. Talk talk business type asoral the idea to describe to implies.

Base words: retseptiv speech, interferensiya, sintagmatik, paradigmatic, psixolingvistika, reproduksioya, the psychiatrist.

ACCESS:

Speaking of psychological content looks at ifhis surge in the form of “the idea” (review) indications record to be necessary.

These terms , in English “utterance”, nemischa in the “aussage”, ruschada “viskazivanie” as referred.

Talk as a result of we mindedarni free say we can. Exactly the same idea is to say which is the motivation, needs to speak force of will. The questions are short-short answers also or entire headed monolog also “ Opinion statement” is called.

“ Foreign language teaching of the psychiatrist theoretical umumlashma thebee according, speech communication process it is not,speak not,talk-talk yanglig’ activities during the idea to realize to and express to a method”

Talk to any idea, describe to order in a particular language grammar vocabulary and pronunciation in the event of applying is. The students foreign language to speak to teach

the space for practical purposes are listed. That education initial a few of the year lastida they talk and listen, to understand, learn, reading and writing teaching tool to serve the will. So do, talk 3 task was:

- 1) Communication tool
- 2) Teaching tool
- 3) Teaching practical purpose (listen to understand and to read too high in class so that position is able. Writing while the goal is not, only the means of the function it performs)

Speaking of incredibly perfect at the level to be “ spontaneous” (spontaneous involuntary committed would be) speech in the name of received. A word with the words, “Free nutq” to say that acceptable it will be.

Foreign language talk in three parts and consists of the speech activity.

Initially to speak tendency i.e. the motivation you need will.

This language by means of the idea to say was moderated by the need yug'iladi. The speech act to perform the desire appears when, any information to giveto the question, the answer qayatrish or the speech act (please, for example, command) select execution qilishwhga is entered. Talk of this part cannotteeth of intention (English intentsya, English “ interest”) in appearance is, it's just that they are.

The idea of a declaration part , while the analysis-synthesis of the practice of work into falls. Do this to memory to keep (assotsiativ connection) service will. Paradigmatik and sintagmatik connection mavjud. Paradigmatik in communication with the internal links of the words different character according to be compared it is observed that; I a kind but in writing the difference that make the words (see-seat, two-too); the meaning is close to (big-savage s); contrary meaning to the words (go-comes here-there). To speak to teach sintagmatik communication importance is huge it is, in the words of the various combinations to be applied will will keep.

Talk of the third part of the execution to; the idea is to describe to, the pronunciation to, that is, the foreign speech in him talking from ash 's.

The three part follow to be the point of activity from the type of talk that they bring. Of speech occur to on scientific problems of modern psixolingvistika in the research (academician a. a. Leontyev, academic Zimnyaya i. a. and others in the works) wide, lit.

The idea oral statement to (to talk) - train of thought in a written statement, itself is the speech perception of fahmlab to (listening and reading comprehension) , such as speech activities types with a logical link without established are.

Bar far speech activity in the type of as-is, speak also to itself, the specific mechanisms are there. Speak out increase to educational the appropriate number psixofiziologik mechanisms developed to be should. Such mechanisms about short comments keltis iri.

1) Reproduksiya engine

(Speech in the process of some elements training without if used, some of the new creation)

2) The choice of mechanism

(Words and speech samples elected said of a difference to go)

3) The combination mechanism

(the speaker of the words and the sentence combination development in the process of previous language experience , which met the new compounds formation)

4) Drafting mechanism

(to talk qualification status possessing reader comment statement in the rules , despite the subject the speech activity be doing)

5) Pre - feeling mexanigido you n

(fluent speak to speech in the flow of what to say in advance notice go, it last labor ready stand)

6) Diskursivlik engine

(if pre - fahmlab bomirtish way with the speech to prepare have, diskursivlik using speak of at uzuk that go process management, speak the speech tactics and the strategy is implemented can be)

The notional part of speech function in the sentence I cert. The notional part of speech are:

- 1) It was completely
- 2) Adjective
- 3) Pronoun
- 4) Numeral
- 5) Verbal

- 6) Adverb
- 7) Words of the category of state
- 8) Modal words
- 9) Interjection

The emphasis is on the structural relations between words or speech either by hand or by express words by me or hand technique. They never any independent function in the sentence. Here heong waist:

- 1) Preposition
- 2) Conjunction
- 3) Particle
- 4) Article

The conclusion to make that to say it is noteworthy, language tools using the idea , describe to be somewhat of a difficult night. Because this process is a time at two different speech program fulfillment on comes: one thought related to that is the idea of maintaining aspect is, ikkinfeel the language of the unit is to use.

Today, the time intensity with I want to change and this changes most of the first is all a lot feeling is one - of young people. Fortunately, young people, their period requirements with the combination of is . But the same time of the self may forget. We kimmiz, how great' the breed of the world our generation that calling their heart is always in resonance- imaging - giving, self - faithful to remain motivated I stood!

Sh.M. Mirziyoyev

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